

Interrelationship between protein content and degree of polish of milled rice

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Rice continues to be the most important food source in the world, with about 20% of the global population depending on it as a major staple food (Singh 1992). Degree of polish is one of the most important parameters considered during milling for trading. It affects the proximate composition of milled rice, milling yield, and whiteness value, which influence the overall economics of the production system.

Rice protein is unique among cereal proteins, being the richest in glutelin and lowest in prolamin. Ellis et al (1986) noted that regular milling removes all the pericarp, seed coat, nucellus, a major portion of the aleurone layer, embryo, and an insignificant amount of the nonaleurone endosperm except from the lateral ridges. Similar work has been reported by Juliano et al (1973), Pandey and Sah (1990), and Pal Veena et al (1999). Although some researchers have attempted to correlate the extent of degree of polish on removal of bran and

protein content, no systematic work has been reported on the mathematical modeling of these parameters. This study was undertaken to explain the interrelationship between degree of polish and protein content of milled rice.

Four common rice varieties (Manhar, Govind, Pant Dhan 4, and Type 3) were collected from the Department of Plant Breeding, Pantnagar, to ensure genetic purity. Experiments were designed to vary the degree of polish by changing the milling time from 0 to 110 s at 10-s intervals. Degree of polish was computed as the ratio of cumulative bran removed and brown rice. A sample of 150 g of unconditioned rice was taken and later conditioned to $13 \pm 1\%$ (db) for the entire experiment. Dehusking and polishing were done using a Satake dehusker and polisher. Weighed brown rice was fed into the polisher for 10 s. After polishing, milled rice and bran were collected separately. Milled rice

(milled for 10 s) was again polished for another 10 s. A similar procedure was followed for the different sets of samples until the milling time of 110 s was completed. Milled rice samples of different varieties with varying milling times were analyzed for protein content (Kjeldahl method, AACC [1962]). Crude protein content was calculated for different samples of milled rice.

The degree of polish of milled rice ranged from 0% to 11.43%, whereas protein content varied from 4.69% to 8.95%. Data revealed that protein content decreased as the degree of polish increased for all varieties (Table 1). This may be due to a nonuniform distribution of protein, since, within the endosperm, the outer layer has been shown to have a much higher concentration of protein than the whole kernel. The rate of decrease did not appear to be constant (Table 1) for the test varieties. The loss of protein content during 110 s of polishing was minimum (4.43%) for

Table 1. Degree of polish and protein content of milled rice.

Time (s)	Manhar		Govind		Pant Dhan 4		Type 3	
	Degree of polish (%)	Protein content (%)	Degree of polish (%)	Protein content (%)	Degree of polish (%)	Protein content (%)	Degree of polish (%)	Protein content (%)
0	Nil	8.95	Nil	8.69	Nil	8.00	Nil	7.17
10	1.37	7.16	2.37	7.77	1.50	7.52	1.43	6.96
20	2.73	7.13	4.11	7.48	2.88	7.40	2.86	6.94
30	3.73	6.95	5.72	7.23	4.19	7.24	3.90	6.90
40	4.55	6.79	6.99	7.00	5.12	6.96	4.77	5.81
50	5.26	6.50	7.93	6.68	5.97	6.81	5.51	5.80
60	5.95	6.27	8.66	6.42	6.67	6.45	6.24	5.59
70	6.59	6.01	9.31	6.25	7.32	6.17	6.92	5.43
80	7.11	5.80	9.86	6.19	7.89	5.90	7.47	5.37
90	7.57	5.46	10.41	6.10	8.45	5.59	7.96	5.30
100	7.99	5.14	10.93	5.85	8.99	5.40	8.41	5.16
110	8.39	4.78	11.43	5.40	9.50	5.21	8.84	4.69

Type 3. The protein content of milled rice after 110 s ranged from 4.3% to 5.4%, which indicates a loss of 30–50%. Hence, excessive polishing is detrimental not only in terms of not breakage but also nutrient loss.

Attempts were made to develop prediction models between protein content of milled rice and degree of polish. The modeling of protein vs degree of polishing relationship was considered in linear, semilogarithmic, and polynomial models of second- and third-order forms. Table 2 gives the resulting models along with the associated statistical parameters.

The regression coefficient (*r*) for linear and semilogarithmic models ranged from 0.87 to 0.97, whereas, for second- and third-order polynomial models, the *r*

value indicated a high correlation coefficient (0.99). The standard error of the estimate (SEE) was considerably lower for semilogarithmic models than for linear models. It was consistently lower for second- and third-order polynomial models. On the basis of regression coefficients and the SEE, polynomial models can perform better than other tested models.

It may be concluded that milling time strongly influenced protein content in milled rice. Excessive polishing can result in a considerable loss of protein in milled rice (2.48–4.43%), depending on variety, at 8–11% degree of polish. The protein content of milled rice can be estimated within 7.14% prediction error using a third-order polynomial.

References

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Table 2. Accepted models for protein content vs degree of polish.^a

Variety	Models (Pr/Dp)	<i>r</i>	SEE	<i>E_M</i>	<i>E₉₀</i>
Manhar	Ln (Pr) = 2.124861 – 0.5577 Dp	0.93	0.0534	2.27	5.14
Manhar	Pr = 8.076650 – 0.33928 Dp	0.94	0.0279	3.62	6.28
Manhar	Pr = 6.926385 + 0.227489 Dp – 0.05619 Dp ²	0.99	0.074	0.78	1.03
Manhar	Pr = 7.260756 – 0.06362 Dp + 0.011486 Dp ² – 0.00459 Dp ³	0.99	0.064	0.63	1.15
Govind	Ln (Pr) = 2.171384 – 0.03674 Dp	0.97	0.0292	1.08	1.66
Govind	Pr = 8.527198 – 0.24428 Dp	0.98	0.155	1.62	2.58
Govind	Pr = 7.896996 – 0.02878 Dp – 0.01526 Dp ²	0.91	0.102	1.15	2.56
Govind	Pr = 8.229708 – 0.21886 Dp + 0.015045 Dp ² – 0.00144 Dp ³	0.99	0.104	1.11	2.34
Pant Dhan 4	Ln (Pr) = 2.1546 – 0.04855 Dp	0.96	0.0395	1.70	2.81
Pant Dhan 4	Pr = 8.355399 – 0.31024 Dp	0.97	0.218	2.64	4.53
Pant Dhan 4	Pr = 7.507885 + 0.066535 Dp – 0.03344 Dp ²	0.99	0.0636	0.69	0.56
Pant Dhan 4	Pr = 7.266054 + 0.254605 Dp – 0.07213 Dp ² + 0.00232 Dp ³	0.99	0.0584	0.55	0.75
Type 3	Ln (Pr) = 2.059753 – 0.05257 Dp	0.96	0.146	1.63	3.94
Type 3	Pr = 7.635754 – 0.31147 Dp	0.95	0.246	3.12	5.85
Type 3	Pr = 7.520631 – 0.25749 Dp – 0.00508 Dp ²	0.95	0.259	3.17	6.31
Type 3	Pr = 6.894650 + 0.261082 Dp – 0.11971 Dp ² + 0.00739 Dp ³	0.96	0.263	3.01	5.56

^a*E_M* = mean error, %; *E₉₀* = error based on 90% data, SEE = standard error of the estimate. Pr = protein content, Dp = degree of polish, Ln = natural log.

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